

Using Project-Based Tasks in Mother Tongue Classes

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Abstract. *The article covers information about project-based education and project tasks, the stages of project implementation, views on the proper organization of educational and project activities. The importance of using project-based tasks in teaching the mother tongue is revealed. There are also examples of project tasks intended for use in mother tongue classes.*

Key words: *project-based education, educational project activity, project work, project stages, native language education, native language textbooks.*

Today, the main goal of school education is to educate not only a graduate who can recite theoretical information from memory, but also a person who can directly apply the knowledge he has learned in practice, has his own independent opinion, and can conduct a critical analysis of any topic. It is known that skills such as critical thinking, communication, creativity, information and media literacy, digital literacy, flexibility, and initiative are recognized as the skills of the 21st century, and it is precisely these skills that the student has in the educational process. special attention is paid to the formation of skills. The use of modern technologies and effective teaching methods will give positive results in achieving this goal.

Educational technologies are one of the important factors that ensure the quality and effectiveness of the teaching process. Project technology, which entered pedagogy in the last century and has not lost its relevance to this day, greatly helps students to develop skills based on the 4K model (critical thinking, collaboration, creativity, communication).

Project technology is a problem-based assignment for students, and their target activity; it is a form of organization of relations between teachers and students, as well as between students [1;112]. According to N.Y. Pakhomova, each project has a specific problem. If there is no problem, there is no activity. The problem in the project determines the motivation of the activity aimed at solving it. Educational project is a didactic tool that allows students to create a project and is a process aimed at solving problems that arise in certain situations on the way to completing the task. In this way, the student presents his project by performing several steps, such as choosing an idea/problem for the project, setting a goal, dividing tasks, working on the project, and obtaining the result. In this case, together with the result of the project, the process of its implementation and the path to the result are extremely important. It is in this process that the student applies his theoretical knowledge in practice, skills turn into skills. Also, this technology is of great importance in forming the qualities of determination, responsibility, teamwork in the student.

The concept of "educational project activity" is also used in the use of project education technologies in educational practice. Educational project activity is a set of actions consistently performed by students in order to achieve the educational goal or solve a problem or problematic situation [2;75].

Systematic organization of the process, step-by-step implementation of the work, and the correct implementation of the students' activities are important in the application of project technology. In

the literature, the stages of project work are presented by pedagogues and methodologists in different forms, but they are united by a common structure. We recommend organizing the project preparation activities in the following stages:

1. Introduction to the project. At this stage, the following is done:

- a) the teacher announces the problem selected for the project and discusses it with the students;
- b) clearly defining the goal (giving the student a clear idea of why the project work is being carried out and what result is expected at the end);
- c) dividing students into groups if the project work is collective in nature. In the group, information is given that each participant has a separate task, that everyone should perform the assigned task on time and with quality, and also that individuality is taken into account along with the ability to work in a team when evaluating the project. It is better to leave the distribution of roles in the group to the discretion of the students. The teacher only gives his recommendations.

2. Research process. At this stage, the following is done:

- a) the research methods chosen by the students, the work plan, the expected expected result, the distribution of tasks among the participants are briefly discussed;
- b) students study relevant sources, collect information, sort and organize them;
- c) participants conduct individual and collective activities independently;
- d) the results are summarized, a presentation is prepared, work is carried out on the aesthetic aspects and design of the work;

3. Completion of the project. At this stage, the following is done:

- a) project presentation and protection processes are carried out;
- b) the prepared projects are discussed together: the practical importance of the work, achievements and shortcomings, the activities of the participants are discussed;
- c) project work is evaluated.

The main goal of the educational projects is focused on the purposeful organization of the student's activities, the formation of the skills of independent thinking, working with information, and conducting research in the process of problem solving and project implementation. Project technology, which was first actively used in fields such as engineering, construction, and sculpture, has proven itself to be one of the most effective methods in all areas of education, especially in language teaching.

It is known that today the communicative approach is given priority in mother tongue education. This approach mainly focuses on the student's ability to communicate, to apply the rules of the language in practice, to develop oral and written speech, listening and reading comprehension skills together with linguistic skills. The use of project-based assignments can be beneficial in achieving these goals. The updated 5th, 6th, and 10th grade Mother tongue textbooks also include project-based tasks. In particular, in the 6th grade, preparation of a business plan, development of a set of social and moral rules; In the 10th grade, it is planned to work on interesting educational projects, such as preparing a speech for the stage, making a short film.

The use of project education technology in mother tongue classes is important for the implementation of the following goals:

- strengthening of the studied theoretical material with the help of direct practical application;
- conscious assimilation of the content of grammatical rules, being able to distinguish language units in practice;
- to be able to work with various information, to form the skill of sorting them;
- achieving oral and written literacy;

- formation of students' creativity, creativity, independent thinking skills, etc.

Also, while working on projects, qualities such as team work, responsibility, and research develop in students.

Project technology differs from other educational technologies in that it requires a specific product to be prepared by a student or a team of students at the end of the work. At the end of the activity, the results will be presented by the project participants, and the achievements and shortcomings will be analyzed together.

You can work with the following types of educational projects in mother tongue classes:

- preparation of wall newspapers, posters, advertising banners;
- preparation of various booklets, brochures, collections;
- creating dictionaries on a specific topic (spelling, explanatory, pictorial, multilingual dictionaries...);
- independent preparation of newspapers and magazines or their pages;
- preparation of radio speeches, interviews, podcasts;
- types of work related to text editing can be used.

When working with the types of projects considered above, it is necessary to take into account the age of students, their level of knowledge, abilities, the duration and complexity of the project work. It is appropriate to assign relatively simple project work to be completed individually, and large-scale projects to be completed in a group or collective manner.

Below is a sample project assignment that we used during the experimental process. This project work is intended for students of the 7th grade and is prepared in accordance with the topic "Social networks" in the 7th grade Mother tongue textbook. Project work is done individually.

Stage 2: brief information about the content and purpose of the project is given; the condition of the task, the instructions for execution are explained.

Task: preparing a post on the topic "Culture of behavior in comments on social networks" in the Telegram messenger (choosing the title within the topic is optional). Before the next lesson, students should determine the purpose of the project and study comments on social networks.

Stage 2: students' goals are listened to a project plan is drawn up.

Readers comment on their goals and what they focus on when writing a post. Students' opinions are listened to and necessary guidance is given. Also, the tasks to be performed by students are clearly defined;

- monitoring and analyzing comments on posts, audio and video content in social networks;
- Preparing a post on the topic "Culture of behavior in comments on social networks" in Telegram messenger;
- distribute the prepared post to groups and collect the highest number of views.

Stage 3: Readers post their posts and it's decided who gets the most views. This work can be done online in the Telegram group.

Stage 4: at the end of the project, the winning students will be awarded and the posts will be discussed.

The language, style, spelling of the text written by the students is analyzed to what extent they were able to convey the idea. Optionally, the number of winners can be increased, readers can be awarded in several nominations (the most critical post, the most meaningful post, the post with the most reactions...).

This project work is an example of small project types, the duration covers 2 weeks. The goal of this project is to develop students' written speech skills, the ability to express their thoughts clearly,

concisely, and with examples. It also helps to form the qualities of critical analysis and creative thinking in the student. Distributing the post to groups and collecting views is a helpful tool to achieve the goal. Because it is very difficult to get a student interested in just writing a text today. Taking into account the daily lives and interests of students gives them additional motivation.

In conclusion, it can be said that the use of project-based assignments in mother tongue classes encourages students to be active, creative, and research-oriented. One of the greatest achievements of project education is the strengthening of theoretical knowledge of the language in practical activities, the use of acquired skills and competencies by the student directly in the research process. Properly organized educational and project activity serves as an important tool for achieving positive results in education.

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